

The Effects of Polyethylene Glycol (PEG-600) On the Acute Neurotoxicity of Different Types of Pesticides

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Abstract

Pesticides intoxication has been implicated in many toxic diseases, and agricultural adjuvants including polyethylene glycols are used in a variety of applications including industrial manufacturing. The aim of this study was to analyze the effect of PEG-600 on the biochemical toxic effects of malathion, imiprothrin and imidacloprid on the basis of the determined LD₅₀ values on the quails (Coturnix coturnix). In the present study the toxic effect of the tested pesticides was characterized by a clear disturbances in the activity of plasma alkaline phosphatase (ALP), transaminases (AST, ALT), acetylcholinesterase (AChE) and total contents, as well the concentrations of brain glutamate, aspartate, GABA, glycine, norepinephrine and dopamine concentrations.

PEG-600 treatment did not change blood biochemical parameters but significantly increases the concentrations of whole brain studied amino acids and catecholamines. In addition, the combination of PEG-600 with the tested pesticides acts synergistically on reducing the recorded LD₅₀ values of malathion, imidacloprid and imiprothrin in Coturnix coturnix by -32.247, -41.529 and -11.026; attenuates more toxic symptoms, modulates more changes in the activity of plasma AChE, ALP, AST, and ALT and attenuates more decreased effect in the concentration of the brain dopamine and norepinephrine, and potentiate more toxic effects of the studied pesticides on the concentration of the free studied amino acids. These results could indicate the toxic effect of polyethylene glycol to birds and is also potentiate the neuronal toxic effect of pesticides exposure

Keywords: Pesticides; PEG-600; Amino acids; Monoamines

Introduction

Most efforts in toxicology are devoted to safety evaluation, so considerations must be given to maximize the biological efficiency of the existing pesticide formulations by certain additives including adjuvant that decreases the rates of insecticide application (Hofstee and Gaskin, 2003; Bjorklund et al., 2009; Nobels et al., 2011). Agricultural adjuvants are used to perform different specific functions including wetting, spreading, sticking, and the tested pesticide spray drift (Paveglio et al., 1996; Sharma and Singh 2001). On the other hand, the use of adjuvant nowadays is not concerned only with agricultural application but it also extends to include additives for different types of medications (Lussier et al., 2004). Polyethylene glycol (PEG) and polyether are used in a variety of applications including industrial manufacturing (Barish and Goddard, 2011; Abdel-Mohsen et al., 2012), and pesticides formulations (Krogh et al., 2003, Kumar et al., 2010). PEG is currently the only water soluble polymer, widely accepted in therapeutics with market approval

for different drugs (Veronese and Mero, 2008; Banerjee et al., 2012). Lewis (1991) and Gorzerino et al. (2009) confirm that pesticides and pharmaceutical adjuvant interaction has not been regulated under the US Federal pesticides because little is known about their bioavailability, environmental fate and physiological effects. Regarding their side effects, results of previous studies have indicated that some of agricultural adjuvants are toxic to various species (Lewis, 1991; DelValls et al., 2002), including fish (Parr, 1982), daphnia (Comber et al., 1993), frogs (Edgington et al., 2004) and birds (Rogers, 1974). Other investigators remark that adjuvant may cause adverse effects to laboratory animals and humans (Fata et al., 2002; Stills, 2005). On the other hand, it is known that PEG esters, which are widely used for medicinal treatments or pesticidal applications or agricultural adjuvant, have severe clinical (Bendele et al., 1999), behavioral (Rodrigue et al., 2011), biochemical (Wieder and Davis 1983) and histopathological effects (Ishida et al., 2006). Little data has been known about the neurotoxic effect of PEG adjuvant which is administered individually or in

combination with the commonly-used pesticides. The present study focuses on the effect of PEG-600 on the acute neurotoxicity of malathion, imiprothrin or imidacloprid, on the basis of 1/4 LD₅₀ for each of the adult quail (*Coturnix coturnix*).

Materials and Methods Experimental Animals

The quails (*Coturnix coturnix*) of both sexes weighing (100-150 g) were used in the present study. The animals were housed in standard plastic cages and maintained under controlled laboratory conditions of humidity (45±5%), temperature (22±1°C), and controlled room with 12 h day and night cycle with free access to food and water. Experiments took place between 10:00 and 15:00 h. All the experimental protocols for the use of animals in this study were reviewed and approved by Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee (IACUC). Efforts were made to minimize suffering and reduce the number of animals used.

Pesticides and adjuvant

Malathion: An organophosphate pesticide, has the chemical formula C₁₀H₁₉O₆PS₂ (diethyl dimethoxyphosphinothiol) thio butanedioate). It was denoted by Novartis Egypt (95% pure). The indicated dose level was 145.7 mg/kg dissolved in corn oil.

Imidacloprid: A nitromethylene compound has the chemical formula (1-(6-chloro-3-pyridylmethyl)-N-nitroimidazolidin-2-ylideneamine). It was donated by Novartis Egypt (35% pure). The indicated dose level was 4.5 mg/kg dissolved in corn oil.

Imiprothrin: Pyrethroid insecticide, has the chemical formula (2,5-dioxo-3-(2-propynyl)-1-imidazolidinyl) methyl 2,2-dimethyl-3-(2-methyl-1-propenyl) cyclopropane carboxylate), (50% pure). It was donated by Novartis Egypt (50% pure). The indicated dose level was 456 mg/kg dissolved in corn oil.

PEG-600: Polyethylene glycol 600 dilaurate (PEG-600) was available in emulsifier form. It was donated by the Egyptian Company of Starch, Yeast and Detergents in emulsifier form with an average molecular weight of 600. It is a clear viscous liquid at room temperature.

Adjuvant-pesticides dose preparation

Adjuvant-pesticide mixtures were prepared by mixing the tested dose level of the selected pesticides dissolved in 1 ml of corn oil with PEG-600 glycol (5g %) on the basis of (1:1) volume.

Toxicity testing

One hundred and eighty mature quails were used for toxicity testing studies (LD₅₀ values). The experimental animals were divided into six groups; each was divided into five subgroups consisting of 6 animals each. The animals of each group were orally administered with different doses of the selected pesticides individually or in combination with PEG-600 adjuvant. The number of the dead animals was counted 24 hours post oral application. The probit analysis was used to calculate the lethality percentiles of the studied toxicants by aid of NCSS 2007 software. After LD₅₀ stock solutions were prepared on the basis of 1/4 LD₅₀ values of the studied toxicants.

Animal grouping and treatments

After 2 weeks of acclimatization, 80 animals of nearly a similar weight were selected and animals were separated into 8 groups once daily of treatment: Control group (1 ml corn oil); PEG-600 group (1ml 5%); malathion alone group (145.7 mg/kg in 1 ml corn oil); malathion+PEG-600 (145.7mg/kg malathion in 1 ml corn oil + 1 ml 5%PEG), Imidacloprid alone (4.5 mg/kg in 1ml corn oil); Imidacloprid+PEG600 (4.5 mg/kg imidicloprid +1 ml 5%PEG); Imiprothrin alone (456 mg/kg in 1 ml corn oil) and Imiprothrin+PEG-600 (456mg/kg in 1ml corn oil+1ml 5% PEG).

Tissue Preparation and biochemical assays

After 96 hours of administration, the animals were sacrificed by decapitation in the morning to avoid diurnal variations of the endogenous amines, enzymes, and other biochemical molecules. The brain tissue was rapidly removed and homogenized in 0.1 M phosphate buffer (pH 7.8), using a glass-Teflon homogenizer. Tissue homogenates were centrifuged at 10,000 g for 60 min at 4°C and the homogenates were used for the determination of both free amino acids according to Heinrikson and Meredith (1984),

and monoamines, according to Pagel et al. (2000) using HPLC (Perkin-Elmer). At the time of scarification, blood was collected into clean heparinized centrifuge tubes, plasma were separated by centrifugation and used for determination of total protein (Gornall et al., 1949), transaminases (ALT and AST) (Reitman and Frankel 1957), acetylcholinesterase (AChE) by modified Ellman method (Gorun et al., 1978) and alkaline phosphatase (ALP) (Ellis et al., 1971) by using appropriate reagent kits purchased from Biodiagnostic.

Statistical analysis

The data is presented as Mean \pm SE. Statistical analysis is evaluated by One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by LSD (Least significance difference) for comparison between groups using SPSS program version 17.

Joint action analysis Mansour's formula (Mansour et al. 2008) was used to identify the type of interaction in terms of interaction index $\{II = \frac{M+C}{A+B}\}$. M, C, A and B represent the mean values obtained; M for the mixture value; A and B for the values of the individual compounds in that mixture, and C for the control value. Based on the above-mentioned authors view, the rating of interaction is either potentiating ($II \geq 1$), additive ($II=1\pm 0.05$) or antagonistic ($II \leq 1$).

Results Toxicity Testing

The values describing the mortality response to a range of concentrations of the tested pesticides in the presence or absence of PEG-600 are given in Table (1). It is obvious that the potentian is highly recommended; the toxicity of the tested insecticides when administered in combination with PEG-adjuvant is more toxic than do the insecticides alone. In comparison, the recorded LD₅₀ values have been decreased by -32.247, -41.529 and -11.026 more than malathion, imidacloprid and imiprothrin when they are administered individually.

General toxic observations

Animals treated with the selected insecticides, which are administered individually or in combination with PEG-adjuvant, display noticeable behavioral changes

during the experiment. General weaknesses, salivation, sometimes excitation, variable sequence of motor symptoms involving pawing and tremor of the body and convulsions have been developed. These symptoms are observed in all treated groups. The addition of PEG-adjuvant to the selected insecticides has showed a highly-toxic potential more than the insecticide alone.

Plasma biochemical analysis

The present study has revealed that the disturbance resulted in serum enzyme activities and different biochemical parameters of quails is in response to the dispensing of malathion, imiprothrin and imidacloprid pesticides when they are administered individually or in combination with PEG-600 adjuvant. The recorded data has showed significant increase in the activities of ALP, AST and ALT (Fig.1). On the other hand, total protein content and AChE activity has been significantly decreased (Fig.2). The maximal effects, however, have been attained post treatments with imiprothrin-PEG-600 for total protein content, AST, ALT and AChE and with imidacloprid-PEG-600 for ALP.

Brain neurotransmitters Amino acids

Data in Figs.(3,4) shows for the animals which are exposed to 1/4 LD₅₀ of the tested pesticides which is administered individually or in combination with PEG-600 has higher levels of whole brain amino acids more than those of the control groups. The maximal concentrations of glutamate, aspartate and GABA, however, are attained when PEG-6000 is administered individually. On the other hand, maximal glycine concentration is recorded post exposure to imidacloprid when it is administered individually. According to the overall results, antagonistic effect represents 83.33% of the total number of analyzed mixtures towards the four amino acids and potentiative effect accounted only 16.67%.

Monoamines

Regarding the effect of imidacloprid, when it is administered individually or in combination with the

tested adjuvant, recorded data (Table 2) reveals a great depletion in the concentrations of brain dopamine and serotonin. The potent highly-significant effect has been attained post exposure to malathion and PEG. Conversely, the acute toxicants administration has led to a moderate increase of effect in brain norepinephrine concentration. Moreover, the maximal highly significant change has been attained post exposure to imidacloprid when it is administered individually or in combination with PEG-600. Regarding the interaction indices for monoamines concentration in brain of quails, antagonistic effect represents 66.66 % of the total number of analyzed mixtures towards the three tested monoamines whereas additive effect accounts for only 33.33 %.

Discussion

Many chemicals are regarded as pollutants, ranging from simple inorganic ions to complex organic molecules. Among the pollutants that animals encounter daily are the pesticides which occupy special position. Furthermore, many of the agricultural adjuvant used in the formulations of pesticides present a high likelihood of exposure (Stark and Walthall 2003). Several investigators (Liu and Stansly 2000; Sharma and Singh 2001), have reported that some adjuvants are toxic to certain species and others increase the toxicity of pesticides. The first data reported in this study is concerned with the toxicity syndromes. The observed signs reveal general weakness, salivation, sometimes excitation, tremors and convulsions. These results coincide with Costa (2008) using malathion; Verschoyle and Barnes (1972) and Verschoyle and Aldridge (1980), who have studied the effect of different types of Pyretheroid, and Azevedo-Pereira **et al.** (2011) who have conducted their experiment on the effect of imidacloprid. The mode of actions, however, is mainly attributed to their inhibition to AChE in the nervous system, resulting in the accumulation of the neurotransmitter acetylcholine at the postsynaptic receptor. In the present study, the potential health effects depend upon the kind of the tested pesticide and are in parallel contact with the activity of AChE which shows variable inhibition. The reason for such variability is mainly attributed to pesticide structural differences as well as their differences in affinity for the AChE active sites. This hypothesis is also well confirmed in terms of the dose level, (LD₅₀) and the

determined AChE activity. Imidacloprid shows both the higher toxicity symptoms, higher toxic effect and higher potent effect on plasma AChE as compared with malathion or imiprothrin. Moreover, the characteristic toxicity syndromes of imidacloprid, which belong to a new chemical family of chloronicotynyl compounds, include emaciation, tremors and convulsions. These findings coincide with the results declared by Azevedo-Pereira *et al.* (2011). According to the same author, after 96-hour exposure to imidacloprid, AChE activity, behavior parameters, ventilation and locomotion were reduced and the mode of actions was through action on several types of post-synaptic nicotinic acetylcholine receptors in the nervous system. On the other hand, the clinical symptoms, which are observed during imiprothrin acute exposure, include hypersensitivity, tremors, and motor ataxia which they are mainly due to the higher potency and selectivity of the tested compound against the nervous system of the studied animal. Our data, however, correspond to the observations made by other researchers reporting on the toxicity of pyretheroid pesticides (Dobsíková *et al.* 2006; Velisek *et al.* 2009). According to David *et al.* (2005), Pyretheroid acts on a variety of putative biochemical and physiological target sites, like voltage-sensitive sodium, calcium, and chloride channels. Moreover, the combination of PEG-600 as adjuvant to the tested pesticides has enhanced their potency and revealed more obvious toxicity syndromes. Little is known about the biochemical neurotoxicity effect of PEG-600. The combination of PEG-600 with the tested pesticides might lead to structural modification and potentiating their mode of actions on the central nervous system depression, acidosis, and nephrotoxicity. According to DeSantis and Jones (1999) and Thordarson *et al.* (2006), modification of the protein surface synthetic polymers like PEG is a major problem. In this study, the deleterious effects of PEG, when it is administered individually on the activity of the studied enzymes, are not well-recommended and the prevalence is well-recognized in their combination with the tested pesticides. With the exception of AChE, the activities of ALP, AST and ALT have markedly been increased post treatments with the combined effect. According to Chang *et al.* (1998), PEG stabilizes the enzyme activity to some extent. Andersson and Hahn-Hägerdal (1988) have also reported that high

concentrations of PEG are proton motive force for α -Amylase production. Therefore, pesticide exposure could indicate elevated plasma transaminases and ALP activities by means of a transient damage of different body tissues, whereas PEG allows a state of enzyme release stability. In addition, the more toxicity symptoms produced by pesticide-PEG mixtures may be attributed to the availability of more AChE inhibition. Many researchers postulate that the more Ach accumulation due to AchE inhibition resulted in more tremors and convulsions (Worek et al. 2005; Mohebbi et al. 2001). The mechanism, which is involved in pesticide-PEG 600, is unknown at present. It may suggest that pesticide-adjuvant treatment has more neuronal oxidative stress leading to more free radical formation. Brain cells seem to be vulnerable to this toxic effect since more inhibition in AchE activity and more toxicity symptoms have been recorded.

In the present study, the effect of the tested compounds was also investigated on the brain biochemical change. When the tested ester is administered individually, brain amino acids, DA and 5-HT monoamines are significantly affected and it has no or little effect on the studied plasma biochemical parameters. Moreover, while the tested parameters are highly affected as a result of the tested doses of the selected pesticides when administered individually, moderate modulations in their levels have been attained with the combined treatment with the tested pesticides and PEG-600. The recorded data are in accordance with several approaches studies using different pesticides and different experimental animals; Moulton et al. (1996) in their treatment of the freshwater mussel *Elliptio complanata*; Balani et al. (2011) in their experiment on imidacloprid in male White Leghorn; and Al-Attar (2010) studies on the alterations induced by malathion .

The decrease of serum total protein as compared to control is thought to be due several reasons like the decrease in amino acids uptake, the increase of conversion rate of glycogenic amino acids and the reduction of protein synthesis which in turn may be due to a decrease in the amount and availability of mRNA and DNA. On the basis of the recorded increase in the level of all the studied amino acids, it has been observed that the tested pesticides which are administered individually or in combination with PEG-600 adjuvant, cause inhibition of protein

synthesis which yielded high levels of free amino acids.

Regarding the effect of the tested compounds on the studied biogenic amines, the tested pesticides have variable effects .While brain norepinephrine shows a general increase, there significant reduction in the levels of DA and 5-HT as a result of the imiprothrin and imidicloprid neurotoxicity. More change was observed in the serotonin and nor-epinephrine levels in all groups post the combined effect with the tested ester. PEG-600 alone shows significant decreased change in the levels of DA and 5-HT monoamine. There are several possible mechanisms for the biogenic actions of the tested pesticides such as neuroendocrine disruption

(Cooper et al., 1999), MAO inhibition (Nag and Nandi, 1987);and monoamines metabolism (Xu et al., 2012) and modify the kinetics of voltage-sensitive ion channels and calcium ion flux/homeostasis that could affect the release of several neurotransmitters. Moreover, the recorded change in the brain endogenous may result from pathologic damage changes as recorded in the present investigation. On the other hand, the combination with PEG-600 exhibited more significant catecholamine depletion as compared to pesticides treated animals. However, the combination with organophosphate malathion have a highly potent reductional effect in the 5-HT and DA. Reasonable explanation could be that PEG-600 exerts its effects due to its weak DA releasing, dopamine reuptake and NMDA inhibitory actions. Also, it may suggest that PEG-600 might modulate the membrane potential of nerve cells over a wide range of stimulus which affects synaptic release of the tested biogenic amines and such changes induce cognitive, behavioral and motor coordination defects.

In conclusion, there are clinical trials that have reported the safety and tolerability of PEG-600 in humans and signified the safety and lack of central effects but the present article provides an overview of modulation effect PEG-600 as adjuvant on neurotoxicological effects of different types of pesticides on birds. The proposed mechanisms are potentiation at most of the studied parameters that could be attributed to the influence on neurotransmitters or their metabolism.

References

- [1] A. M. Abdel-Mohsen, R. M. Abdel-Rahman, R. Hrdina, A. Imramovský, L. Burgert, L. and A.S. Aly, Antibacterial cotton fabrics treated with core-shell nanoparticles. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules*, 50: 1245-1253, 2012.
- [2] A. M. Al-Attar. Physiological and histopathological investigations on the effects of alpha-lipoic acid in rats exposed to malathion. *Journal of Biomedicine and Biotechnology*, 203503, 2010
- [3] E. Andersson, and B. Hahn-Hägerdal. High concentrations of PEG as a possible uncoupler of the proton motive force: α -Amylase production by *Bacillus subtilis* and *B. amyloliquefaciens* in aqueous two-phase systems and PEG solutions. *Applied Microbiology and Biotechnology*, 29: 329-336, 1988.
- [4] H. M. S. Azevedo-Pereira, M.F. Lemos and A.M. Soares. Effects of imidacloprid exposure on *Chironomus riparius* Meigen larvae: Linking acetylcholinesterase activity to behavior. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety*, 74:1210-1215, 2011.
- [5] T. Balani, S. Agrawal and A.M. Thaker . Hematological and biochemical changes due to short-term oral administration of imidacloprid. *Toxicology International*, 18, 2-4, 2011.
- [6] S. S. Banerjee, N. Aher, R. Patil, R. and J. Khandare. Poly (ethylene glycol)-Prodrug Conjugates: Concept, Design, and Applications. *Journal of Drug Delivery Article ID103973*, 17 pages doi:10.1155/2012/103973,2012.
- [7] J. A. Barish and J.M. Goddard. Polyethylene glycol grafted polyethylene: A versatile platform for nonmigratory active packaging applications. *Journal of Food Science*, 76:586-591, 2011.
- [8] A. M. Bendele, J. McComb, T. Gould, J. Frazier, E. Chlipala, J. Seely, G. Kieft and C.K. Edwards 3rd, 1999. Effects of PEGylated soluble tumor necrosis factor receptor type I (PEG sTNF-RI) alone and in combination with methotrexate in adjuvant arthritic rats. *Clinical and Experimental Rheumatology*, 17:553-560, 1999.
- [9] K. Bjorklund, A. P. Cousins, A.M. Stromvall and P.A. Malmqvist. Phthalates and nonylphenols in urban runoff: Occurrence, distribution and area emission factors. *Science Total Environment Journal*, 407:4665-4672, 2009.
- [10] J. C. Chang, J.P. Diveley, J.R. Savary and F.C. Jensen, Adjuvant activity of incomplete Freund's adjuvant. *Advanced Drug Delivery Reviews*, 32:173-186, 1988.
- [11] M. H. I. Comber, T.D. Williams and K.M. Stewart, The effects of nonylphenol on *Daphnia magna*. *Water Research*, 27:273-276, 1993.
- [12] R. L. Cooper, J.M. Goldman and T.E. Stoker Neuroendocrine and reproductive effects of contemporary-use pesticides. *Toxicology and Industrial Health*, 15(1-2):26-36, 1999.
- [13] L. G. Costa. Toxic effect of pesticides. In: C. D. Klaassen (Ed.), Casarett and Doull's Toxicology. The Basic Science of Poisons. (7th ed.). New York, NY: McGraw-Hill, pp. 883-930, 2008.
- [14] J. P. David, C. Strode, J. Vontas, D. Nikou, A. Vaughan, P.M. Pignatelli, C. Louis, J. Hemingway and H. Ranson. The *Anopheles gambiae* detoxification chip: A highly specific microarray to study metabolic-based insecticide resistance in malaria vectors. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 102:4080-4084, 2005.
- [15] T.A. DelValls, J.M. Forja and A. Gómez-Parra, .Seasonality of contamination, toxicity, and quality values in sediments from littoral ecosystems in the Gulf of Cádiz (SW Spain). *Chemosphere*, 46:1033-1043, 2002.
- [16] G. DeSantis, and J.B. Jones. Chemical modification of enzymes for enhanced functionality. *Current Opinion in Biotechnology*, 10:324-330, 1999.
- [17] R. Dobsíková, J. Velíšek, T. Wlasow, P. Gomulka, Z. Svobodová and L. Novotný. Effects of cypermethrin on some haematological, biochemical and histopathological parameters of common carp (*Cyprinus carpio* L.). *Neuroendocrinology Letters*, 27:91-95, 2006.
- [18] A. N. Edgington, P.M. Sheridan, G.R. Stephenson, D.G. Thompson, and H.J. Boermans. Comparative effects of pH and vision herbicide on two life stages of four anuran amphibian species. *Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry*, 23:815-822, 2004.
- [19] G. Ellis, A. Belfield, and D.M. Goldberg. Colorimetric determination of serum acid phosphatase activity using adenosine 3'-

- monophosphate as substrate. *Journal of Clinical Pathology*, 24:493-500, 1971.
- [20] F. Fata, A. Mirza, G. Craig, S. Nair, A. Law, J. Gallagher, N. Ellison and A. Bernath. Efficacy and toxicity of adjuvant chemotherapy in elderly patients with colon carcinoma: a 10-year experience of the Geisinger Medical Center. *Cancer*, 94:1931-1938, 2002.
- [21] A. G. Gornall, C.J. Bardawill and M.M. David. Determination of serum proteins by means of the biuret reaction. *The Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 177:751-66, 1949.
- [22] V. Gorun, I. Proinov, V. Balaban, G. Balaban and O. Barzu. Modified Ellman procedure for assay of cholinesterase in crude enzymatic preparations. *Analytical Biochemistry*, 86:324-326, 1978.
- [23] C. Gorzerino, A. Quemeneur, A. Hillenweck, M. Baradat, G. Delous, M. Ollitrault, D. Azam, T. Caquet, and L. Lagadic. Effects of diquat and fomesafen applied alone and in combination with a nonylphenol polyethoxylate adjuvant on Lemna minor in aquatic indoor microcosms. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety*, 72:802-810, 2009.
- [24] R. L. Henrikson and S.C. Meredith. Amino acid analysis by RP-HPLC precolum derivatization with phenyl isothiocyanate. *Analytical Biochemistry*, 136:165-175, 1984.
- [25] M. E. Hofstee and R.E. Gaskin. Phytotoxicity of agrochemical adjuvants on avocados. *Plant Protection Products*, 56:274, 2003.
- [26] T. Ishida, W. Li, Z. Liu, and H. Kiwada. Stimulatory effect of polyethylene glycol (PEG) on gene expression in mouse liver following hydrodynamics-based transfection. *Genetic Medicine Journal*, 8:324-334, 2006.
- [27] K. A. Krogh, B. Halling-Sørensen, B.B. Mogensen and K.V. Vejrup. Environmental properties and effects of nonionic surfactant adjuvants in pesticides: A review. *Chemosphere*, 50:871-901, 2003.
- [28] J. Kumar, N.A. Shakil, M.K. Singh, M.K. Singh, M.K., A. Pandey and R.P. Pandey, Development of controlled release formulations of azadirachtin-A employing poly (ethylene glycol) based amphiphilic copolymers. *Journal of Environmental Science and Health, B*, 45:310-314, 2010.
- [29] M. A. Lewis. Chronic and sublethal toxicities of surfactants to aquatic animals: A review and risk assessment. *Water Research*, 25:101-113, 1991.
- [30] T. X. Liu and P.A. Stansly. Insecticidal activity of surfactants and oils against silverleaf whitefly (*Bemisia argentifolii*) nymphs (Homoptera: Aleyrodidae) on collards and tomato. *Pest Management Science*, 56:861-866, 2000.
- [31] S. A. Mansour, T.M. Heikal, A.H. Mossa and A.A. Refaie. Toxic effects of five insecticides and their mixture on male albino rats. *J. Egypt. Soc. Toxicol.* 39, 85-94, 2008. In: T. Satoh, R.C. Gupta (Eds) *Anticholinesterase Pesticides: Metabolism, Neurotoxicity, and Epidemiology*, John Wiley & Sons, 2011.
- [32] D. Lussier, G. Angela, A.G. Huskey, K. Russell and R.K. Portenoy. Adjuvant Analgesics in Cancer Pain Management the *Oncologist* September, 9:5 571-591, 2004.
- [33] F. Mohebbi, R. Ahmadi, A.M. Azari, L. Esmaili and Y. Asadpour. On the red coloration of Urmia Lake (Northwest Iran). *International Journal of Aquatic Science*, 2:88-92, 2011.
- [34] C. A. Moulton, W. James Fleming, C.E. Purnel. Effects of two cholinesterase-inhibiting pesticides on freshwater mussels. *Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry*, 15:131-137, 1996.
- [35] M. Nag and N. Nandi. In vitro and in vivo effect of organophosphate pesticides on monoamine oxidase activity in rat brain. *Bioscience Reports*, 7 (10):801- 803, 1989.
- [36] I. Nobels, P. Spanoghe, G. Haesaert, J. Robbens, and R. Blust. Toxicity ranking and toxic mode of action evaluation of commonly used agricultural adjuvants on the basis of bacterial gene expression profiles. *PLoS ONE* 6, e24139, 2011.
- [37] P. Pagel, J. Blome and H.U. Wolf. High-performance liquid chromatographic separation and measurement of various biogenic compounds possibly involved in the pathomechanism of Parkinson's disease. *Journal of Chromatography B: Biomedical Sciences and Applications*, 746:297-304, 2000.
- [38] J. F. Parr. Toxicology of adjuvants. In: *Adjuvants for Herbicides*, WSSA, Champaign, IL. Pp.93-114, 1982.

- [39] F. L. Pavoglio, K.M. Kilbride, C.E. Grue, C.A. Simenstad and K.L. Fresh. Use of Rodeo and X-77 spreader to control smooth cordgrass (*Spartina alterniflora*) in a southwestern Washington estuary: 1. Environmental fate. *Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry*, 15:961-968, 1996.
- [40] S. Reitman, and S.A. Frankel. Colorimetric method for the determination of serum glutamic oxalacetic and glutamic pyruvic transaminases. *American Journal of Clinical Pathology*, 28:56-63, 1957.
- [41] J. R. Rodrigue, W. Balistreri, B. Haber, M.M. Jonas, P. Mohan, J.P. Molleston, K.F. Murray, M.R. Narkewicz, P. Rosenthal, L.J. Smith, S.J. Lobritto, K.B. Schwarz, P.R. Robuck, B. Barton and R.P. González-Peralta, Peginterferon with or without ribavirin has minimal effect on quality of life, behavioral/emotional, and cognitive outcomes in children. *Hepatology*, 53:1468-1475, 2011.
- [42] J. C. Rogers. Responses of caged red-winged blackbirds to two types of repellents. *Journal of Wildlife Management*, 38:418-423, 1974.
- [43] S. D. Sharma and M. Singh. Surfactants increase toxicity of glyphosate and 2, 4-D to Brazil pusley. *HortScience*, 36:726-728, 2001.
- [44] J. D. Stark and W.K. Walthall. Agricultural adjuvants: acute mortality and effects on population growth rate of *Daphnia pulex* after chronic exposure. *Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry*, 22:3056-3061, 2003.
- [45] H. F. Jr. Stills. Adjuvants and antibody production: dispelling the myths associated with Freund's complete and other adjuvants. *The ILAR Journal*, 46:280-293, 2005.
- [46] P. Thordarson, B. Le Droumaguet and K. Velonia . Well-defined protein-polymer conjugates- synthesis and potential applications. *Applied Microbiology and Biotechnology*, 73:243-254, 2006.
- [47] J. Velisek, Z. Svobodova and J. Mackova. Effects of bifenthrin on some haematological, biochemical and histopathological parameters of common carp (*Cyprinus carpio* L.). *Fish Physiology and Biochemistry*, 35:583-590, 2009.
- [48] F. M. Veronese and A. Mero. The impact of PEGylation on biological therapies. *BioDrugs*, 22:315-329, 2008.
- [49] R. D. Verschoyle, and W.N. Aldridge. Structure-activity relationships of some pyrethroids in rats. *Archives of Toxicology*, 45: 325-329, 1980.
- [50] R. D. Verschoyle and J.M. Barnes. Toxicity of natural and synthetic pyrethrins to rats. *Pesticide Biochemistry and Physiology*, 2:308-311, 1972.
- [51] K. J. Wieder, and F.F. Davis. Enzyme therapy: II. Effect of covalent attachment of polyethylene glycol on biochemical parameters and immunological determinants of beta-glucosidase and alpha-galactosidase. *Applied Biochemistry and Biotechnology*, 5:337-347, 1983.
- [52] F. Worek, M. Koller, H. Thiermann, L. Szinicz. Diagnostic aspects of organophosphate poisoning. *Toxicology*, 214:182-189, 2005.
- [53] L. Xu, H. Tian, W. Wang and S. Ru. Effects of monocrotophos pesticide on serotonin metabolism during early development in the sea urchin, *Hemicentrotus pulcherrimus*. *Environmental Toxicology and Pharmacology*. 6; 34(2):537-547, 2012.

Table 1. Lethal Dosage (LD₅₀) Values of the tested pesticides individually or in combination with PEG600

Pesticide	LD ₅₀ (mg/g)	Pesticide-Adjuvant	LD ₅₀ (mg/kg)	% of toxicity increased value
Malathion	583	Malathion-PEG	395	32.247
Imidacloprid	17.02	Imidacloprid-PEG	15.98	41.529
Imiprothrin	1823	Imiprothrin-PEG	1622	11.026

Table 2. The effect of pesticides and/or PEG600 on brain monoamines of quail (*Coturnix coturnix*)

Group	Concentration (µg/g fresh tissue)	
	Norepinephrine	Dopamine
Control	510.57±11.49	1371.65±30.85
Malathion	511.80±17.33	454.92±31.40*
Imiprothrin	613.28±8.77*	1019.39±42.82*
Imidacloprid	663.68±52.02*	1242.47±67.28*
F-value	5.08 [#]	65.48 [#]
PEG-600	500.38±46.70	879.67±37.57
Malathion-PEG	398.68±11.22 ^{*a} _n	267.99±12.17 [*] _{an}
Imiprothrin-PEG	523.67±37.65 ^{an}	1022.43±56.58 ^{*an}
Imidacloprid-PEG	690.90±18.17 ^{*a} _d	1050.02±33.21 ^{*an}
F-value	14.48 [#]	91.24 [#]

Data is expressed as Mean± SE (n=6). *Significant (P<0.05): Pesticide treated group as compared to control group and Pesticide-adjuvant as compared to PEG-treated group. F-

value for One-way analysis ANOVA (LSD) between groups in the same column # Significant (P<0.05), an= antagonism, ad= Additive, Po= Potentiation.

Fig.1: The effect of pesticides and/or PEG600 on the plasma AST, ALT and ALP activity of quail (*Coturnix coturnix*).

Data are expressed as Mean±SE (n=6). *Significant (P<0.05): Pesticide-treated group as compared to control group and Pesticide-adjuvant group as

compared to PEG-treated group. an= antagonism, ad= Additive, Po= Potentiation.

Fig.2 : The effect of pesticides and/or PEG600 on the plasma total protein content and AChE activity of quail (*Coturnix coturnix*).

Data are expressed as Mean±SE (n=6). *Significant (P<0.05): Pesticide-treated group as compared to control group and Pesticide-adjuvant group as

compared to PEG-treated group. an= antagonism, ad= Additive, Po= Potentiation

Table3: The effect of pesticides and/or PEG600 on brain glutamate and aspartate concentration in the brain of quail (*Coturnix coturnix*).

Data are expressed as Mean± SE (n=6). *Significant (P<0.05): Pesticide treated group as compared to control group and Pesticide-

adjuvant group as compared to PEG-treated group. an= antagonism, ad= Additive, Po= Potentiation.

Table4. The effect of pesticides and/or PEG600 on GABA and glycine concentration in the brain of quail (*Coturnix coturnix*).

Data are expressed as Mean± SE (n=6). *Significant (P<0.05): Pesticide treated group as compared to control group and Pesticide-adjuvant group as compared to PEG-treated group. an= antagonism, ad= Additive, Po= Potentiation